

Organic Derivatives of Boron. Part I. Synthesis by Alcohol Interchange Technique

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The reactions of ethyl borate with butanols (*n* & *tert.*), ethylene glycol, catechol, salicylic acid, and anthranilic acid have been studied in different stoichiometric ratios in refluxing benzene. The alcohol produced has been removed azeotropically with benzene; the advantages of this technique have been discussed.

The following compounds have been synthesised by the above procedure: ethyl dibutyl^aborate, ethyl ethyleneborate, diethylene ethylenedi-(borate), ethyl and butyl^f *o*-phenyleneborates, tri-*o*-phenylene-bis-borate, borosalicylic acid, ethoxyboron anthranilate.

Alcohol interchange technique has been extensively employed by one of the authors and also others for the preparation of derivatives of aluminium (Mehrotra, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 585; 1954, 31, 85), titanium (Bradley, Mehrotra, and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2027, 4204), zirconium (Mehrotra, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 904; Bradley and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 280), niobium (Bradley *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1958, 99), and uranium (Bradley *et al.*, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 260). The advantages of the azeotropic distillation of ethanol or isopropanol, produced in reactions of this type, have been emphasised in a recent publication (Mehrotra, *loc. cit.*).

In spite of very active interest in the field of similar derivatives of boron, the technique of alcohol interchange has been employed to a very limited extent. This technique was first employed in the case of boron by Wuyts and Duquesne (*Bull. Soc. Chem. Belg.*, 1939, 48, 77) to prepare organo-boron compounds. Several compounds were prepared by them by distilling a mixture of the alcohol or phenol with a 25% excess of propyl^a borate. Propanol formed during the reaction was removed by distillation at atmospheric pressure and the excess of propyl borate was distilled off at a reduced pressure.

Thomas (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 820, 823) also applied the same technique, taking a slight excess of alcohol or phenol in place of borate, to preparation of those compounds, which could not be prepared from boric acid or oxide and alcohol.

Thus the azeotropic distillation technique of alcohol interchange does not appear to have been used in the case of boron at all. Apart from the advantage of employing only a slight excess of the alcohols or other reagents and removing the ethanol produced azeotropically with benzene, the technique has the unique advantage that reactions in required stoichiometric proportions can be carried out with its help. Thus an attempt has been made to prepare mixed alkoxides of boron by the following simple reactions:

Although stable mixed derivatives could not be prepared in the case of acyclic alcohols (*n*- and *tert.*-butanols), the technique has readily furnished stable mixed compounds with glycol and catechol. Further syntheses of salicylate and anthranilate derivatives have been attempted by the new technique.

(a) *Normal Alkoxides*.—The reaction between ethyl borate and butanol¹ is very fast and tributyl borate can be quantitatively prepared from ethyl borate by taking almost the theoretical quantity of the alcohol.

When the reaction is carried out in 1 : 2 molar ratio with a view to preparing the mixed borate B(OEt)(OBu)_2 , two moles of ethanol are, however, removed azeotropically, as found by analysis, indicating that the reaction :

has gone to completion. Compound (I) on distillation, however, undergoes disproportionation, affording a mixture of B(OEt)_3 , $\text{B(OEt)}_2(\text{OBu})$, B(OEt)(OBu)_2 , and B(OBu)_3 .

Previously Schiff (*Annalen Suppl.*, 1867, 5, 183) had claimed to have prepared such compounds by heating two tri-alkyl borates together. Later, similar experiments were carried out by Thomas (*loc. cit.*) by refluxing a mixture of two alcohols (3 g. moles of each), boric anhydride, and benzene and allowing the condensed vapours to percolate through anhydrous copper sulphate to remove the water formed during the reaction, and distilling the mixed borate formed under reduced pressure. He showed that such acyclic mixed borates disproportionated readily on distillation and observed that Schiff's claim rested on fortuitous analyses of the appropriate distillation cuts.

(b) *Tertiary Alkoxides*.—The reaction of ethyl borate with butanol¹ is comparatively very slow and almost stops after the replacement of two moles of ethoxy group, thus affording the mixed borate $\text{B(OC}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ (II).

The actual formation of (II) in solution is supported by the extremely slow nature of the reaction after two moles of ethanol have been distilled. Similar observations have been made in the case of aluminium ethoxide-butanol¹ interchange (Mehrotra, *loc. cit.*) and these have been ascribed to steric hindrance to the replacement of the third alkoxy group. This compound also disproportionates, however, on distillation although the rate of disproportionation is slow as even the last fraction after double distillation of the compound is not a pure sample of butyl¹ borate.

(c) *Glycolates*.—The reaction between ethyl borate and ethylene glycol in equimolar ratio gives rise to a compound with replacement of two moles of ethoxy group, corresponding to the formation of ethyl ethyleneborate (III). When the reaction is carried out in 2 : 3 molar ratio, diethylene ethylenedi-(borate) (IV) is formed.

The above two compounds have been previously prepared by Blau *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4116); compound (III) by the action of ethanol on ethylene chloroboronate and (IV) by the interaction of BCl_2 and ethylene glycol in 2 : 3 molar ratio. Although these compounds provide

similar analytical data, compound (III) differs in physical properties, the cause of which is under investigation.

(d) *Catecholates*.—Reaction between ethyl borate and catechol in equimolar ratio furnishes the compound, ethyl *o*-phenyleneborate (V). The alcoholysis of ethyl *o*-phenyleneborate with butanol¹ affords butyl¹ *o*-phenyleneborate (VI).

When ethyl borate and catechol are allowed to react in 2 : 3 molar ratio, tri-*o*-phenylene-bisborate (VII) is obtained, which has also been prepared from boric acid and catechol by removing the water formed during the reaction azeotropically with benzene.

Previously Gerrard *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1529) prepared compound (V) by the action of ethanol on *o*-phenylene chloroboronate and compound (VII) by reacting BCl_3 and catechol in 2 : 3 molar ratio. Compound (VI) is a new one. The preparation of the new compound (VI) by a simple replacement reaction shows in a pronounced degree the advantage of the new technique, as the reaction of butanol¹ with *o*-phenylene chloroboronate will fail in this case to produce compound (VI) due to the side reaction of butanol¹ with hydrogen chloride.

(e) *Salicylate*.—Ethyl borate reacts with salicylic acid in 1 : 2 molar ratio, giving out all the 3 moles of ethanol with the formation of *borosalicylic acid* (VIII).

When the reaction is carried out in equimolar ratio, the same compound is formed, half of ethyl borate remaining unchanged.

Foelsing (D.R.P., 230,725 ; 288,388) described the preparation of a zinc salt of borosalicylic acid and the free acid, but Meulenhoff (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1925, **44**, 150) could not repeat the preparation of either of them though he prepared a number of other salts of borosalicylic acid. Preparation of boron trisalicylate has been reported by Hirao and Yabwichi (*J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1954, **74**, 1073) from boric acid and salicylic acid, and by Ahmad, Haider, and Khundkar (*J. Appl. Chem.*, 1954, **4**, 543) by the action of salicylic acid on boron triacetate, but their work is doubtful in view of the results reported by Gerrard and Mooney (*Chem. & Ind.*, 1958, 227).

(f) *Anthranilate*.—Anthranilic acid reacts with ethyl borate in equimolar ratio, furnishing *ethoxyboron anthranilate* (IX) according to the following scheme :

The above is a new type of reaction showing the easy replaceability of ethanol groups simultaneously by an amino and a carboxylic acid group in *ortho* position in the benzene ring. The synthesis and the identity of the compound have been confirmed by repeated analyses and molecular weight measurements in ether. Incidentally, the reaction of benzoic acid with ethyl borate will give rise to ethyl benzoate according to the following scheme (Hirao and Yabwichi, *loc. cit.*):

The reaction of ethyl borate with aniline was attempted by Jones and Kinney (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 1378), who reported negative results. On refluxing ethyl borate with excess aniline for 10-12 hours, boron tri-anilide (in very low yield) could, however, be synthesised according to the reaction :

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable joints was used throughout and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Fractionations were carried out in a column (30 inches) packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total-condensation variable-take-off stillhead.

Benzene (B.D.H.,L.R.) was dried over sodium and redistilled. Butyl' alcohol (B.D.H.,L.R.) was dried over calcium oxide, followed by distillation over sodium butoxide'. Other alcohols were dried by the usual procedures and were finally purified by careful fractionation.

Ethyl borate was prepared from boric oxide and ethanol (Webster and Dennis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 3233), removing the water formed during the reaction as a ternary azeotrope of water, ethanol, and benzene.

Analytical Methods.—Boron was determined by hydrolysing the compound and titrating the boric acid formed with sodium hydroxide in presence of mannitol. In those compounds, which gave acids or bases besides boric acid on hydrolysis, boron was estimated by Thomas' method (*loc. cit.*).

Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Ethoxide was determined by a back-titration method (Bradley and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450). The method of estimation is not affected by the presence of butanol' or butoxide' group (Mehrotra, *loc. cit.*). Salicylic acid was determined by alkaline permanganate method.

Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in benzene and ether by a semi-micro ebulliometer (Gallenkamp) employing thermosistor sensing. Concentrations were plotted against ΔR (decrease in resistance) and a straight line was obtained in each case.

Reaction between Ethyl Borate and Butanol.—To ethyl borate (9.3 g.) in benzene (50 g.) was added butanolⁿ (16 g.) and the mixture was refluxed at bath temperature of 120-30° for half an hour. The azeotrope coming at 68° was then slowly taken. Ethanol obtained in the azeotrope was 8.75 g. (3 moles require 8.79 g.). The excess of benzene was distilled off at a high reflux ratio. Finally butylⁿ borate (13.2 g.) was distilled at 128°. [Found: B, 4.71. Calc. for B(OC₄H₉)₃: B, 4.7%].

Ethyl borate (12.61 g., 1 mole) in benzene (40 g.) and butanolⁿ (12.8 g., 2 moles) were refluxed for half an hour at bath temperature of 120-30°. The azeotrope coming at 68° was then slowly taken. Ethanol obtained in the azeotrope was 7.8 g. (2 moles require 7.95 g.). Excess of benzene was removed and the compound was distilled at 25 mm pressure. First fraction (5 g., B 7%) distilled between 60° and 85° and the second fraction (12.5 g., B 5.1%) distilled between 85° and 97°. [Calc. for B(OEt)₃: B, 7.4% and for B(OBu)₃: B, 4.7%].

Reaction between Ethyl Borate and Butanol.—To ethyl borate (10.83 g.) excess of butanolⁿ and benzene were added five to six times and each time the mixture was refluxed for 4-5 hours. The temperature of the distillate was about 68° in the beginning, but rose to nearly 70° after a few drops were taken out. For the rest of the reaction the distillate, consisting of azeotropic mixtures of ethyl and butylⁿ alcohols and benzene, was slowly collected between 70° and 71° and ethanol was determined in it every time. After 6.8 g. (2 moles require 6.82 g.) of ethanol had been removed, the reaction almost stopped as the temperature of the distilling liquid did not show any tendency of lowering below 73° (b.p. of benzene-butanolⁿ azeotrope) and this was confirmed by lack of reducing power (tested with K₂Cr₂O₇) of the distillate. Excess of benzene and butanolⁿ was distilled off and the compound was distilled at 20 mm pressure. First fraction (3 g.) distilled up to 40°, smelt like benzene, and it was rejected. Second fraction (2.5 g., OEt 15.5%) was obtained between 40° and 60° and the third fraction (7 g., OEt 10.1%) was obtained between 60° and 75°. Third fraction was redistilled. [Found: OEt, 8.8; B, 4.9. Calc. for B(OBu)₃: B, 4.7%].

Reaction between Ethyl Borate and Ethylene Glycol.—Ethyl borate (11.76 g., 1 mole) in benzene (50 g.) was refluxed with glycol (4.99 g., 1 mole) for an hour at bath temperature of 120-30°. The azeotrope coming at 68° was then slowly taken. Ethanol obtained in the azeotrope was 7.3 g. (2 moles require 7.41 g.). Excess of benzene was removed at 30°/5 mm. A colorless semisolid (9.4 g.) was obtained. (Found: B, 9.3. Calc. for C₄H₈O₃B: B, 9.3%).

Ethyl borate (12.18 g. 2 moles) in benzene (50 g.) was refluxed with glycol (7.76 g. 3 moles) for 2 hours at bath temperature of 120-30°. The azeotrope coming at 68° was then slowly taken; 10.51 g. of ethanol (6 moles require 11.5 g.) was obtained in the azeotrope. On removing the excess of benzene at 30°/5 mm, a white powder (8.4 g., m.p. 160-62°) was obtained. [Found: B, 10.6. Calc. for B₂(O₂C₂H₄)₃: B, 10.7%].

Reaction between Ethyl Borate and Catechol.—Ethyl borate (7.76 g., 1 mole) in benzene (40 g.) was refluxed with catechol (5.85 g., 1 mole) for 2 hours and the azeotrope coming at 68° was then slowly taken; ethanol obtained was 4.69 g. (2 moles require 4.89 g.) in the azeotrope. Excess of benzene was distilled off when ethyl *o*-phenyleneborate was obtained as a colorless liquid (6.63 g.), distilling at 86°/8 mm, 0.86 g. remaining undistilled. (Found: B, 6.45. Calc. for C₆H₄O₂BOEt: B, 6.6%).

Ethyl *o*-phenyleneborate (3.1 g.) in benzene (35 g.) was refluxed with butanol^l (4 g.) for 2 hours; the azeotrope coming at 68° was taken slowly; 0.82 g. ethanol (1 mole requires 0.97 g.) was obtained. After removing the excess of benzene, butyl^l *o*-phenyleneborate was obtained as a colorless liquid (3.6 g., 90%), distilling at 85-87°/3 mm. (Found: B, 5.5; M.W., 197. $C_8H_4O_2$ -BOBu requires B, 5.6%; M.W., 192).

Ethyl borate (7.3 g., 2 moles) in benzene (40 g.) was refluxed with catechol (8.25 g., 3 moles) for 3 hours and the azeotrope, taken as usual, gave 6.72 g. ethanol (6 moles require 6.9 g.). Excess of benzene was distilled off and tri-*o*-phenylene-bis-borate (7.5 g.) was distilled at 214°/4 mm., 1 g. residue remaining undistilled. The compound solidified at once. [Found: B, 6.1. Calc. for $B_2(C_6H_4O_2)_3$: B, 6.3%].

A mixture of boric acid (4.74 g., 2 moles), catechol (12.62 g., 3 moles), and benzene (50 g.) was refluxed for 2 hours and then slowly fractionated. After distilling the azeotrope of water and benzene, excess of benzene was distilled rapidly. Tri-*o*-phenylene-bis-borate was distilled at 214-18°/4 mm. (12.72 g.). [Found: B, 6.15. Calc. for $B_2(C_6H_4O_2)_3$: B, 6.3%].

Reaction between Ethyl Borate and Salicylic Acid.—Ethyl borate (6.20 g., 1 mole) in benzene (40 g.) was refluxed with salicylic acid (11.71 g., 2 moles) for 2 hours and the azeotrope taken at 68° furnished 5.4 g. ethanol (3 moles require 5.85 g.). After distilling the excess of benzene, the compound was dried at 30°/5 mm. After washing it with dry ether, borosalicylic acid was obtained in 10.75 g. yield. It is soluble in acetone and ethyl acetate. [Found: B, 3.53; $C_7H_4O_3$, 96. $B(C_7H_4O_3)_2H$ requires B, 3.8; $C_7H_4O_3$, 95.7%].

Ethyl borate (7.88 g., 1 mole) in benzene (45 g.) was refluxed with salicylic acid (7.43 g., 1 mole) for 2 hours. The azeotrope at 68° gave 3.6 g. ethanol (1.5 moles require 3.72 g.). After removing the excess of benzene, the compound was washed with ether several times and dried at 30°/5 mm. Borosalicylic acid obtained was 7.2 g. [Found: B, 3.57; $C_7H_4O_3$, 96.7. $B(C_7H_4O_3)_2H$ requires B, 3.8; $C_7H_4O_3$, 95.7%].

Reaction between Ethyl Borate and Anthranilic Acid.—Ethyl borate (5.32g., 1 mole) in benzene (50 g.) was refluxed with anthranilic acid (4.99 g., 1 mole) for 2 hours. The azeotrope at 68° gave 3.2 g. of ethanol (2 moles require 3.35 g.). The compound was crystallised in benzene. The mother liquor was decanted and the compound was washed with dry benzene. Ethoxyboron anthranilate obtained (6.1 g.) was purified by sublimation at 120-40°/3mm. (Found: B, 5.55. N, 7.01; M. W., 206. $C_9H_{10}O_3NB$ requires B, 5.7; N, 7.33%; M. W., 191).

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